

**THE IMPACT OF IJAYE-EGBA ALLIANCE OF 1860-1862 AGAINST
IBADAN ON INTRA AND INTER-GROUP RELATIONS**

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CERTIFICATION

I hereby certify that this work was carried out by **AINA, Oluwajuwon Ifeoluwa** with Matric Number **168210020** in the Department of History and International studies, Faculty of Arts, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria under the supervision of Prof (Mrs) A. T. Ajayi.

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DEDICATION

This project is dedicated to the God Almighty who has preserved me through the bad and good time of life to see the end of this course successfully.

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ABSTRACT

The Ibadan-Ijaye war broke out in 1860 between Ibadan and Ijaye over who to succeed the old Oyo Empire as the political head of Yorubaland. The two rebelling towns sprang up from the ruins of the old Oyo Empire which was destroyed in 1836 by the Fulanis. Ibadan, ijaye and the new Oyo (Oyo Atiba) succeeded the old Oyo empire after its destruction. The war was a feud among three brothers over how to share common properties. The three brothers, Ibadan, Ijaye and Oyo-Atiba failed to conclusion on who should succeed the old Oyo as the political head of Yorubaland. The last straw that broke the camel's back was the succession issue to the throne of Oyo-Atiba after the death of Alaafin Atiba Atobatele in 1859. Ibadan supported the idea that Atiba's son should succeed him so as to ensure the continuation of the Ibadan tribute policy. Kurumi of Ijaye opposed this claiming it was against the tradition of throne succession in Oyo. Kurumi's opposition was supported by the Egbas and the Ijebus. Ibadan saw this as another attempt to bring an end once more to the unity of Yoruba land and vowed to prevent this by all means. Ibadan did not want Kurumi, the then Are-Ona-Kakanfo, to become another disobedient Afonja. It was on this ground that the Ibadan-Ijaye war broke out in 1861. The Ibadan-Ijaye war was fought in the forest between Ibadan and Ijaye towns. The Egbas supported Ijaye in order to prevent Ibadan from becoming a colossus in Yorubaland. The Ijebus also supported in order to foil Ibadan's attempt of creating enmity between them and Remo in order to secure a route to the coast. Ibadan retaliated by blockading Ijaye from food supplies. Other towns supporting Ijaye retreated immediately. The Egbas were displeased with the actions of Remos and Ikorodus, and therefore sought to punish them but the British army prevented this by fighting and defeating the Egba army.

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CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the study

Generally, Yoruba kingdom or town hardly fought their wars alone. To them, wars presented occasions for the formation of new alliances and new relation with other towns, or villages as well as strengthening or breaking of old ones. Military alliances are formed for various reason, some of these can be summarized as follows: the desire of a weak kingdom or town to eek the aid of its stronger and friendlier neighbors against its enemy; the need for a number of kingdoms or towns to take joint military action against a growing imperial power that threatened their independence and to protect their political and economic interest against external aggression.¹

As warfare became endemic in Yoruba land in the nineteenth century, formation of Military alliance either for offensive or defensive purpose became a common feature of inter-kingdom or inter-town relations². One of this is the Ijaye-Egba alliances of 1860-1862 against Ibadan. This alliance has some implications in

¹The details of this war can be found in S. A. Akintoye revolution and power politics in Yorubaland 1840-1893 (Longman, 1971) and B.A Awe, "The end of an experiment: The collapse of the Ibadan Empire, 1877-1893", Journal of the historical society of Nigeria, 3, 2, 1915; pp 22-230.

²For details see Toyin Falola and Dare Oguntomisin, the military in 19th century Yoruba politics (university of Ife, press) forthcoming chapter two

the inter- and intra-group relation among Yoruba towns especially between Ibadan and Ijaye-Egba relations.

1.2 Objective of the study

The objective of this study is as follow:

- I. To give an in-depth study of the reasons and the impact of the alliances on Ijaye and the Egba
- II. It attempts to provide analysis of how the Egba and the Ijaye allied against Ibadan and their reasons for such alliances.
- III. To ascertain historical trends in the alliance and its implication.
- IV. To provide a case study for inter- and intra-group relation occasioned by war efforts.
- V. To access the impact implication of such alliances for the inter and intra-group relations between the Ibadan and the Ijaye on the Other hand and Ijaye and Egba on the other hand in the second half of 19th century.
- VI. To provide reasons why Ijaye-Egba alliances against Ibadan failed.
- VII. To stimulate discussions and encourage case-studies on the various military alliances formed in Yorubaland in te course of the 19th century Yoruba war
- VIII. To show or demonstrate that tribal interest or identity preservation more than other considerations account for alliances.

1.3 Scope of the study

The study shall cover discussions on Ijaye-Egba military alliance between 1860 and 1862.

It shall discuss the reasons for the alliances and the implication of such alliances for intra- and inter-group relations in Yorubaland.

It shall also discuss the impact of the alliance on the Ijaye and the Egba.

1.4 Research methodology and problems

The sources of this work include primary source (oral tradition) and archival materials. Extensive use is made of secondary sources such as published and unpublished works, articles and pamphlets. A good number of books, pamphlets and dissertations were got from the library archival materials, were got from the National archives at Ibadan, Kaduna and Jos. Although it is important to point out that these archival materials have their limitations. They are however useful to a very large extent. They have been very helpful as supplement to oral tradition.

Oral testimonies were also used in this research. In fact, oral testimonies form a major part of this essay. Those interviewed include notable historians and scholars who have written on Yoruba wars, Ibadan-Ijaye war and some high chiefs of Ibadan, Ijaye and Egba.

Some of these informants were active participant in the events; they were questioned about or inherited stories of the issues being raised. Those interviewed gave very useful information.

In a study of this nature, there is bound to be problems in gathering information because the event occurred in the 19th century. Apart from this, each of the sources employed has its own peculiar problems, the secondary source for example supplied, in some cases limited information and thus one has to look into many works by various authors in order to get a specific idea on the subject matter of this work.

The archival materials were very few as regards their relevance to this study. Moreover one is faced with the problem of damaged materials and misplacement of files.

In spite of these problems, they were overcome with patience and determination to succeed in writing the study.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 SOCIO ECONOMIC SITUATION OF IBADAN IN THE 19TH CENTURY

Ibadan indigenous population remained a largely rural. Over half its totals of adult males were engaged in agriculture. Ibadan has three thousand and more hamlets of full-time farmers. At the time of major religious festivals, the town population swells, at the heights of the farming season it shrinks.

Indigenous Ibadan is fairly typical, in its social structure of most Northern Yoruba towns. To some extent these remain separate settlements, the social life of one scarcely impinging on the other. Yet economically, they are dependent on one another, and the fortunes of the older area are becoming increasingly associated with those of the newer.

Traditional Ibadan: - Ibadan people lived in huge compounds, often containing several hundreds of inhabitants. In the past these were structures of a series of enclosed rectangular courtyards, today only one of such intact compound remains in Ibadan, that of Aremo at Ade-Oyo³.

In a compound, (with a few exceptions) the descendants in the male line of one of the powerful immigrants of early or mid-19th century, together with their wives,

³Samuel Johnson, the history of the Yorubas (Lagos, 1921) p.504.

selected mostly from nearby compounds. A description of the composition of one quarter in Ibadan that of Oje, is given below by Barbara Lloyd.

The lineage is strong corporate body of men and women. In it are vested rights, amounting to ownership, in both towns and farming land. Its members elected from among the female members, a Mogaji who represents their interests in the traditional governing councils and who aspires to a chieftaincy title, settling him on the ladder towards the highest political offices⁴.

Farming is characterized by a simple technology- the hoe, cutlass and axes are the main tools. There is a considerable variety of staple food crops, the notation of which, together with the matching of soil to species calls for considerable skills. All the farming is carried out by men; their wives in the hamlets are engaged in gathering food for domestic use or gathering manufactured products for the markets. The great distance between farm and town compound, together with the degree of specialization practiced by the farmers, gives rise to the complex pattern of markets between producers and consumers. Through the same series, the

⁴Toyin Falola, " The political system of Ibadan in the 19th century" in J.F Ade Ajayi, and B. Ikara, The evolution of Nigerian political system (university press ltd) forthcoming.

imported goods pass from Ibadan merchants and wholesalers to their ultimate purchasers both in the city and at the farm⁵.

Craft industries were highly developed among the Yoruba. Many of these were, and still remain, hereditary occupations within certain lineages⁶.

The traditional political system of Ibadan differs markedly from that of other Yoruba towns. Ibadan has no sacred king as oba - a fact which may be explained by the peculiar origin and early growth of the town. Men, usually the mogaji of their lineage are appointed the chiefs to vacant titles in the lowest rank. As each chief dies, those ranked below him rise in theory one place, thus creating vacancy at the bottom (in practice some leap fogging of places is recorded)⁷.

At the apex of the power hierarchy is the office of the Bale – since 1935 termed Olubadan. Such a system results in the highest political offices being held by the elderly men⁸.

Religion- each lineage has its own cult usually brought to Ibadan by the immigrant founder. Some of these are of the major duties of the Yoruba pantheon, whilst others are little known. All the lineages participate in the egungun celebration, a

⁵Oral interview: Ibadan duets-in-council, February, 2020.

⁶I .BAkinyele, Iweitan Ibadan (England, 1950, 3rd edition) p.111.

⁷Ibid p.111

⁸Ibid

type of ancestor cult. Ibadan's main festival is however associated with OKE IBADAN⁹, a hill near the Eleyele waterworks which legends connect with the founding of the town. To the oke Ibadan deity is ascribed the function of creating fertility.¹⁰

⁹Ibid

¹⁰Johnson, p.605.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 THE IJAYE-EGBA MILITARY ALLIANCES 1860-1862

3.1 General Reasons:

The Ijaye-Egba alliances was formed principally to prosecute the Ijaye war; 1860-1862. The major contending parties in the war were Ijaye and Ibadan, two military towns that emerged from the ruins of the old Oyo empire. The issues at stake in the war have been adequately examined by J. F Ajayi and Robert Smith as the need to emerge Yoruba political leadership after the fall of Oyo Alaafin. These issues centered generally on power politics in Yorubaland in the nineteenth century and specifically on the succession of Adelu the Aremo (crown prince) to the throne of Oyo in 1859 contrary to the Oyo-Yoruba tradition which stipulated that the latter should die with his father. Samuel Johnson and Ajayi and Robert Smith have clearly demonstrated that the war was fought firstly to determine which of the two towns, Ijaye and Ibadan would emerge as a dominant power in Yoruba land and secondly to Kurunmi, the Are-onakakanfo (commander-in-chief) of the rump of Oyo army and ruler of Ijaye , to accept the change in the convention of succession of the throne of Oyo and recognize Adelu as the new legitimate Alaafin¹¹.

¹¹S. Johnson, the history of the Yoruba' (Lagos, 1973), p. 331, J.F.A. Ajayi and Robert Smith op cit

Apart from the fact that, Yoruba towns were prone to seeking alliances in times of war, the Ijaye-Ibadan war could not be prosecuted exclusively by the two towns for a number of reasons. Firstly, the two towns were comparatively equal in military strength.

In them lived war veterans and descendants of the cream of soldiers who defended the old Oyo Empire against Ilorin – Fulani attacks in the 1820's and 1930's. These soldiers were comrades-in-arms who had known each other's military ability, strategy and tactics. Thus the first clash of Ijaye and Ibadan on the battlefield in 1845 had ended in a stalemate. Consequently, it is imperative for the side wishing to achieve victory in the second clash to solicit for material and military support from other Yoruba towns.

Secondly, as fast growing capitals of the two palatinates into which the remnant of the defunct old Oyo had been by Alaafin Atiba, their wars would involve the participation of many Oyo- Yoruba towns under them. While Ibadan could draw material and military support from the towns and villages in the eastern Oyo- Yoruba land, Ijaye had strongholds in the western part, particularly the economically important upper Ogun area whose human and material resources, it could harness for its war efforts.

Thirdly, as the war also involved a struggle between Ijaye and Ibadan for supremacy in Yorubaland, other non-Oyo Yoruba people who would be affected by its result could not be passive on-lookers.

The above are some of the general reasons why many Oyo- Yoruba and non-Oyo Yoruba towns were involved in the war as allies of either Ibadan or Ijaye. The number of Oyo- Yoruba towns which sided with Ibadan has been variously estimated by Esunola of OrileIjaye, Lanionu, Chief S. O Ojo, the Bada of Saki, and chief Orukola, the Asipa of OrileIjaye as 140, 141, 142, 143 respectively¹². Ijaye drew support from the upper Ogun towns which were still loyal to it. Among the Non-Oyo supporters of Ibadan were Ife and Ijebu-Remo towns while the Ijaye got the backing of Ilorin, Ijebu-ode and Abeokuta. Of all the non-Oyo Yoruba people sympathetic to the Ijaye cause, only the Egba of Abeokuta actually fought on the battlefield alongside the Ijaye soldiers.

3.2Ijaye's specific reasons for the alliances

The Ijaye needed and negotiated for the Egba alliance at the outset of the war because they realized that they were fighting not only against Ibadan but also against Oyo, two formidable enemies that had on the eve of the war, swayed many Oyo-Yoruba towns to their side by military might and appeals to traditional loyalties. For instance, having defeated the Ilorin at the battle of Osogbo in

¹²Oral evidence of chief Onikola, the asipa of OrileIjaye, on 29th January 1997.

c.1840¹³, Ibadan confirmed its military superiority and leadership in the eastern Oyo-Yorubaland whose towns were made to contribute soldiers to aid its imperial campaigns. By 1855, Ibadan had begun to make inroads into Ijaye's territory in the upper Ogun. Between that year and 1860, it sent soldiers to raid Awaye, Iberekodo and Iseyin in a bid to take over political control of these towns from Ijaye¹⁴. Unlike Ibadan, Oyo relied on the traditional loyalties of Oyo- Yoruba towns to the Alaafin to extend its political influence at the expenses of Ijaye. For instance, in the 1950's Atiba took the advantage of the traditional differences of the upper Ogun people to the Alaafin, to draw tribute from some upper Ogun town under Kurunmi's control. Some of these towns especially Okeho, Iganna and Iseyin had to pay tribute to both Atiba and Kurunmi to avoid trouble¹⁵.

Alaafin Adelu who succeeded Atiba was more vigorous in his intrusion into the upper Ogun territory. His contest for authority with kurunmi in this area led to a clash between Oyo and Ijaye soldiers in Okeho on the eve of Ijaye war¹⁶. As a result of the military and political influences of Ibadan and Oyo briefly highlighted above, it is not surprising that the Oyo-Yoruba town which gave military and material aids to Oyo and Ibadan includes the upper ogun towns. For example, apart

¹³A.L Herthesett, *iwekikaakerin Yoruba* (Lagos). CMS publication, n.d, p. 173

¹⁴S. O. Ojo, *iwaitan Yoruba apakini* (Ibadan, the author, 1952), p. 201

¹⁵ For details of the relation between Ibadan and Ilorin, see Toyin Falolaans H. O. Danmole, "Ibadan-Ilorin relation in the 19th century: A study imperial struggles in Yorubaland". *Journal of the Yorubaland*:. Trans. African journal society 14, 1985

¹⁶G. O. Oguntomisin, "New forms of political organization in Yorubaland in the midd 19th century: A comparative study of Kurunmi'sIjaye and Kosoko'sEpe" Ph. D thesis, Ibadan, 1979, p. 250.

from contributing troops to Ibadan army, Iganna was said to also supply arms and ammunitions imported from Sabe to both Ibadan and Oyo soldiers¹⁷.

In view of the above; Ijaye needed an alliance with a major Yoruba power to upset an apparent grand alliance of Oyo- Yoruba towns against it. Abeokuta satisfied this need. By 1835 Abeokuta had proved capable of defending itself against external aggressors¹⁸. It had thereafter, launched and successfully prosecuted imperial campaign in the Egbado territory¹⁹. By 1851, it had decisively repulsed a dahomean attack²⁰. In addition to those military feats, Abeokuta's position near the coast recommended it to Ijaye. The Ijaye could through the alliance, have unmolested access to the coast through Abeokuta and could also induce their Egba allies to refuse accord similar facility to the Ibadan.

Ijaye also wanted to avoid being completely isolated by its enemies. As a result of the struggle for supremacy between it and Ibadan, Ijaye began to suffer progressive isolation from Oyo-Yoruba towns controlled by the former from the 1840's onward. Though few towns under Ibadan deflected to Ijaye side in the Batedo war c.1845²¹, Ibadan subsequent grips over these and other Oyo-Yoruba towns made

¹⁷Ibid. pp. 262-264

¹⁸A.K. Ajisafe history of Abeokuta (Abeokuta, 1964), p. 67

¹⁹. Johnson, op cit. p. 251

²⁰See also Toyin Falola, "Trade in the era of military warfare. In 19th century Yorubaland". Journal of the historical society of Nigeria, forthcoming

²¹Ibid. pp. 81-82

such deflection impossible in 1860. Hostility between Kurunmi and the Alaafin from the 1850's until the former's death further alienated Ijaye from those towns still having predilection for royal authority²². In June that year, he was reported to have tried to end Ijaye's isolation. According to Rev. Adolphus Mann "Are (Kurunmi) tries to be on good terms with the towns independent by his power... no towns towards west, north, or east not on terms of peace with are except Oyo where king of Yoruba resides²³. This peace was however momentary. It was marred by increased struggle for authority in the upper Ogun between Ijaye and Oyo on the one hand and Ijaye and Ibadan on the other. Faced with mounting hostility from Ibadan and Oyo, Kurunmi took the step between 1856 and 1858 which enabled him to enjoy the goodwill of the Egba. For instance, he refused king Gezo's persistence pressure to join Dahomey in a grand alliance aimed at destroying Abeokuta²⁴. Thus on the eve of the war, it was possible for the Ijaye to turn to Abeokuta for support when Ibadan and Oyo had virtually formed a grand alliance against it.

The military alliance rekindled 1845, Egba's military aid to Ijaye. In that year, both Ibadan and Ijaye approached Abeokuta for support but the latter under Sodeke, its military ruler, eventually decided to aid Ijaye²⁵. Like in the 1845 war,

²²K. Folayan, "The Egba and Yoruba-Aja power politics. 1832-1894" M.A. Ibadan 1967, p.78

²³S.O. Biobaku. The Egba and their neighbors (London, 1957), pp. 43-44

²⁴S. Johnson op cit p. 300

²⁵G.O. Oguntomisin, op cit, pp. 251-266

the Ibadan was the first to send deputation to seek the Egba alliances or neutrality. J. F.A Ajayi and Robert Smith relate the transaction between the Ibadan and the Egba thus:

“The Egba had received a deputation from Ibadan asking them either to mediate in the dispute or to ally with Ibadan or at least remain neutral. They had sent emissaries of their own to Ijaye in an attempt to mediate but found te Are implacable. They had sent a friendly message back to Ibadan reporting their failure at Ijaye without committing themselves as to their future action.”²⁶”

After the above mentioned diplomatic exchange between Egba and the Ibadan, the Ijaye’s negotiation team led by Oje, a military chief, approached the Egba with a request for military alliance²⁷. Through their negotiator, the Ijaye impressed on the Egba that Ibadan would attack Abeokuta after destroying their town. Ijaye’s point was made at a time when a rumor was circulating in Abeokuta that Ogunmola was the Otun-balogun (commander of the right wing) of Ibadan had boasted that he would “share the occiput” after shaving “ the crown of the head”

²⁶G.O. Oguntomisin, op cit, p. 269 and 270

²⁷S.Johnson op cit p. 300

which the Egba interpreted to mean that Ogunmola intended to attack their town after destroying Ijaye²⁸.

3.3 Egba's Specific Reasons for the Alliance

Though it was not certain that Ogunmola Olodogbokerilogun issued such a threat and the Egba favorably disposed towards the Ijaye's request not only because of the rumor but also because of the Ibadan's anti-Egba activities²⁹. These include Ibadan's favorable response to Dahomey's diplomatic pressure for a grand alliance to destroy and its incursions into the Egbado territory. In 1856, king Gezo of Dahomey sent emissaries to the Alaafin of Oyo and Ibadan chiefs to negotiate alliance with them against Abeokuta. In June 1857, Alaafin Atiba and Ibadan chiefs reciprocated Gezo's diplomatic mission by sending their own messengers to Dahomey. In 1858, these envoys returned to Oyo and Ibadan loaded with large presents from Gezo³⁰. Thus when Ibadan attacked the Egba towns of Ilugun and Ido in February in 1860 to cut off supply of arms through these towns to Ijaye, the Egba regarded the attack as Ibadan soldiers attempt to link up with Dahomean army threatening to invade Abeokuta at that period³¹. Apart from its exchange of friendly diplomatic missions with Dahomey, Abeokuta's inveterate enemy, Ibadan had been seeking from 1859 to have link with the coast through Egbado. Rev. C.A.

²⁸S. Johnson Ibid. p. 337

²⁹J.F.A. Ajayi and Robert Smith op cit, p. 82

³⁰Toyin Falola: "The foreign policy of Ibadan in the ODU, 22, Jan/July 1982.

³¹CMS CA.2/021 Journal of James Barber, 10 March, 1858.

Gollmer reported in 1859 that he saw a party of Ibadan traders trying to establish an agency in Imeko³².

By that year also, Ibadan's envoys had reached Ketu. By 1860, Ibadan had a direct link with Porto Novo and had established sufficient influence in the Egbado area to make it a base for its campaign against the Egba³³. These activities were regarded by the Egba as inimical not only to their survival but also to their political interests in the Egbado territory.

Apart from the above, the Egba wanted to check Ibadan's expansionist activities. They saw Ibadan as a colossus seeking to dominate Yorubaland. Their feelings towards Ibadan were expressed succinctly by Thomas King, a CMS missionary in 1868³⁴. If Ibadan were tigers everyone must not yield implicit subjection to their ferocity. The Egba would like to ally with the Ijaye to weaken Ibadan and to checkmate its imperial expansion because a military powerful Ibadan struggling to have a direct link to the coast was both a political and an economic threat to the Egba. Consequently, in addition to seeking to stall Ibadan's territorial expansion, the Egba were interested in protecting their middle-man's position by blocking the former's access route to the coast. The alliance with the Ijaye would put them in a strong military position to achieve their aim.

³² CMS CA.2/061 Journal of T. King, 19 February, 1860.

³³ CMS CA.2/043, Annual letter of C.A. Gollmer, 12 Dec, 1861; A.K. Folayan op cit, p. 67

³⁴.Iwelrohin, March, 24, 1860

One important factor that influenced Egba's decision in favor of Ijaye was their nostalgic feelings for their old homes, their former township in the Egba forest. They were driven from their townships by the Oyo and Ife soldiers between 1826 and 1830. According to J.F.A Ajayi and Smith, "the Egba, had by no means forgotten their old homesteads where the ashes of their fathers lay in farms now belonging to Ibadan"³⁵. The alliance, it was hoped would provide them the opportunity to drive away the Ibadan from their homesteads. As a result of the above considerations, the Egba formally declared for Ijaye on 20th march, 1860³⁶. Their army estimated as 20000 warriors arrived Ijaye on 19th may, 1860³⁷.

³⁵ Kemi Morgan, Akinyele's outline history of Ibadan part II (Ibadan, The caxton press, Ltd., n.d.), p. 34.

³⁶ S. Johnson, op cit, p. 41

³⁷ Read to Taylor, 8 April, 1861, S.B.C (University of Ibadan microfilm library).

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 THE IMPACT OF THE ALLIANCE

4.1 Impact on Ijaye

The presence of the Egba warrior in Ijaye immediately relieved its people of the fear of imminent defeat. Between March and May 1860, their town had been closely besieged by Ibadan soldiers that it was dangerous for anybody to sow or reap in the farms outside the town walls without military escort. After the first few engagements, the Ijaye had begun to run short of gunpowder. Kurunmi's arsenal, the only armory in Ijaye, was virtually empty and Ijaye warriors were compelled to rely mainly on their bows and arrows. Consequently, they lost ground rapidly and the Ibadan was able to close in on their town. While they tactically avoided pitched battles, the Ibadan kept on the pressure so as to end the war quickly with a decisive victory. Thus the presence of Egba warriors was timely. Not only did it increase the numbers of the fighting forces in Ijaye, it raised the morale of Ijaye warriors. Kurunmi himself was said to have danced for joy³⁸.

The alliance enabled the Ijaye to have access to Abeokuta for the procurement of arms and ammunitions to recoup their dividing weapons. At a time when the Ijaye were virtually deprived of farming activity outside their town walls and their

³⁸J.F.A Ajayi and Robert Smith op cit. p.39; Kemi Morgan, Akinyele's outline history of Ibadan part two (Ibadan, the caxton press ltd....n.d) p.34

store of provision was grossly inadequate, the alliance was also welcomed relied until December 1860, supplies of provision were coming from the upper Ogun towns of Erin and Iwawin. But the Ibadan warriors destroyed these towns and occupied Ijaye strongholds in Irawo, Awaye and Iseyin, the Ijaye relied on their Egba ally as alternative source of supply of foodstuff and other provisions³⁹.

The alliance made it possible for Christian missionaries to set up a relief committee in Abeokuta to cater for the suffering Ijaye children. Inaugurated in November 1960, the committee appealed for fund from England, Lagos, Badagry, Abeokuta and Sierra Leone. By October 1861, the committee had collected a sum of one hundred and fifty three pounds, eighteen shillings and nine pence (\$153, 18s. 9d.) to Ijaye children kept in the custody of Rev. Adolphus Mann in Ijaye and of other missionaries in Abeokuta and Sierra Leone benefitted from the funds. The custodians were given money by the committee to feed and cater for the children. The money was paid to them quarterly according to the number of Ijaye children under their care. The alliance provided opportunity for large Ijaye refugees to secure permanent settlement in Abeokuta. When Egba warriors withdrew from Ijaye on March 17, 1860, there were exodus of men, women and children from the town to Abeokuta⁴⁰. Abogunrin, Kurunmi's head slave and successor, led the bulk of Ijaye's warrior in an orderly form to Abeokuta before the Ibadan enters the

³⁹ S. Johnson, op cit. p.338; J.F.A Ajayi and Robert Smith, op cit. p.89

⁴⁰Kemi Morgan, op cit. p. 41; S. Johnson, Ibid pp 346-380, G.O. Oguntomisin, op cit pp 286-287

town and set it on fire. The Egba settled these refugees in a new quarter called Ago Ijaye(Ijaye settlement). Though some people escape to Ibadan and other towns in Yorubaland today, Ago Ijaye constitutes the largest concentration of Ijaye people. Like their counterparts, Ijayekukudi, and the Ijayeobirinti, refugees from Ijayemokinaye, the Egbagbagura town occupied by Oyo soldiers in 1831, the refugees in Ago Ijaye had been fully integrated into the Egba socio-economic and political system⁴¹. The negative impact of the alliance on the Ijaye outweighs the positive effects discussed above. Firstly, the presence of Egba warriors in Ijaye led to the escalation of war. Hitherto, the war had been regarded as a dispute among members of the same family. The Bada, Calvary officers, of Ijaye and Ibadan had secretly made an oath to fire gun powder without shots on the battle field⁴². In Ibadan, the pacific Balogun Ibikunle, commander in chief of Ibadan army, reluctantly approved the war⁴³. However, as the Egba entered the war on the Ijaye side, Ibadan nationalism was aroused. The Ibadan warriors who had been divided between the balogun's men who did not favor a full scale war and those of Ogunmola, the otunbalogun (commander of the right wing), the advocate of war, loosened ranks and sent their differences. The Bada of Ibadan broke their oath with their Ijaye counterparts and pursued the war vigorously. In Oyo, opinion about the

⁴¹Iwelrohin, November 22, 1860; CMS (y) 2/3 file No 1: Report of Ijaye Relief Committee 1861 (National Archives Ibadan)

⁴² Toyin Fashola, "The Ijaye in Diaspora: Problems of Integration And Re-settlement, 1862-1895", The Journal of Asian and African studies, Forthcoming.

⁴³Reid to Taylor, 2 November, 1860 Southern Baptist Convention (S.B.C) papers (University of Ibadan Microfilm Library)

war also changed. Hitherto, a Baptist missionary they had been told that the Alaafin had no aim of fighting against the Ijaye people. The intention was to subdue kurunmi so that he could bring back the whole of Yorubaland under his power as in days of his predecessors. But when the Egba became allies of the Ijaye, raid reported the Oyo's changed attitude to the war thus:

“The point of dispute now seems to be who should have the power, the Egba or the Yorubas. Hence, a very important question is involved and one I fear that will not be easily disposed of. Should Ijaye be taken, the Yorubas will have power and then perhaps they will continue the war against the Egbas. If Ijaye is sustained and the Yoruba driven from there, that will the Egbas power and they will perhaps continue the war against the Yoruba.”⁴⁴

It is clear from above that as a result of the Egbas involvement in the war, Ijaye had become a deciding factor in the power struggle between the Oyo-Yoruba and the Egba. The Ibadan and Oyo's aim in the war had shifted from that of

⁴⁴ S. Johnson, op cit p. 333

chastising Kurunmi to the pursuit of total war against Ijaye and its Egba ally. Thus when Kurunmi died in 1861 the war did not end. It continued even after the destruction of Ijaye.

Secondly, the alliance failed to ensure Ijaye survival. The Egba altered Kurunmi's war strategy. Before their arrival, Kurunmi had tactically avoided pitched battles. His strategy was to lure Ibadan warriors to cross the river Ose to his men's side. This was intended to conserve ammunition and to draw Ibadan warriors to a place where they would be vulnerable to Ijaye's attack. The Egba however disagreed with Kurunmi. They were anxious to go to war as soon as they arrived. They grossly underrated the strength of Ibadan warriors whom they thought would easily be captured in thousands. Thus while they were coming to Ijaye, they armed themselves with ropes with which to tie Ibadan captives. In their haste to overrun Ibadan's army in their first encounter on June 4, 1960, they crossed the river Ose in defiance of Kurunmi's warning⁴⁵. They ran into Ibadan's ambush and suffered heavy casualties. According to reports in the *iweirohin*, apart from those killed in the battlefield, several Egba warriors were missing. Among those missing were 450 Owu and Gbagura men and also 60 Hoko warriors and war chiefs⁴⁶. The defeat punctured the confidence of the Ijaye in the Egba's ability to

⁴⁵Reld to Taylor, 8 April, 1861 S.B.C (University of Ibadan Microfilm Library)

⁴⁶ *Ibid*

aid them to victory. The Ijaye women consequently sang the following divisive song against the Egba to express their disappointment:

Onigbejati o to 'gun,

iwi l'akogbodowi

It was our allies that cause our rout,

but we dare not say it is so⁴⁷

In addition to altering Kurunmi's conduct of the war, they refused to integrate their army with the Ijaye's, thereby splitting the command of the armies defending Ijaye⁴⁸. Kurunmi lost absolute control of the offensive and defensive command of the war. This adversely affected the Ijaye's chances of victory because their Egba allies responsible for the split in command were unable to provide effective counterweight to the forces of the Ibadan and its allies.

Unlike Ibadan warriors, the Egba were not experienced in pitched battles which featured constantly in the Ijaye war. They were expert in siege warfare which earned them victory in their wars against the Egbado in the 1830's. their famous siege against Ado in the 1840's and early 1850's lasted for 13 years.⁴⁹ Their musketeers were inexperienced. Unlike the Ibadan musketeers who had been

⁴⁷ Kemi Morgan, op cit p. 35; J.F.A Ajayi and Robert Smith, op cit p. 90

⁴⁸ Iwelrohin, June 23, 1860

⁴⁹ S. Johnson, op cit p. 354

taught to shoot low and aim accurately, they shot so high that they scarcely hit their targets. When Ogunmola observed these defect in Egba warriors he was confident of Ibadan's victory. According to Samuel Johnson, Ogunmola confidently assured the Balogun of victory in the following words:

"Ibikunle, ao se won, ao se won, Egba ko moogunjija

Ibikunle, we shall win, we shall win, the Egba has no knowledge of the art of war".⁵⁰

Indeed, the iweirohin reported few indecisive Egba successes throughout the course of the war.

The Egba army was thus not formidable enough to win victory for Ijaye. Lack of mutual trust also contributed to the alliances failure to save Ijaye from defeat. The Ijaye distrusted their Egba alliances whose ulterior motive to recover their lost homestead had not been hidden. This motive was not only disclosed to the British government but also to the Awujale of Ijebu-Ode. For instance, on April 9, 1861, the Parakoyi chiefs told Consul Foote when they later visited Abeokuta that the Egbas intention was not to draw back until they had recovered the land whereby the ruined homes and graves of their fathers⁵¹. As occupants of parts of these ruined homes, the Ijaye suspected that the Egbas could eventually seize their

⁵⁰ S. Johnson. Ibid p. 339; J.F.A Ajayi and Robert Smith op cit p 89

⁵¹ J. F. A. Ajayi and Robert Smith op cit. pp 72 and 90

towns. Egba's message to the Apena of Lagos in 1883, Balogun Onatowokan, the Commander-in-Chief of Ijebu army, said:

“During the late Ijaye war; the Egba sent to Ijebu to say two

Yorubas are fighting and they are going to flog them...”⁵²

Mutual distrust adversely affected the military input of alliance right from its first engagement. According to Thomas King, a CMS Missionary resident in Abeokuta, the Ijaye failed to hold their ground in the battle of June 4, 1860, because they suspected the Egbas might turn around and take their town, while they themselves were engaged with the enemy⁵³. This mutual distrust seems to have pervaded the conduct of the war between 1860 and 1862. Report of the war carried by the IweIrohin, indicated that the allies on many occasions, avoided combined effort against the enemy. Kurunmi preferred to face the enemy, the enemy alone sending for the Egbas assistance only when his soldiers were hard-pressed. This lapse provided opportunity for Ibadan, on many occasions, to attack the separate camps of Ijaye and Abeokuta simultaneously to disorganize them and weaken their stricken power. The battles of November 4, 1860, July 11 and 23, 1861 and

⁵² S. Johnson, op cit p. 340

⁵³ IweIrohin, May 6, 1861

October 23, 1861, were prominent examples of such attacks by Ibadan warriors on the Ijaye and Egba camps.⁵⁴

As the war progressed and particularly after Ijaye had lost the cream of its army in Erin and Iwawun, it became clear that the Egba were not fighting for the survival of Ijaye per se. on October 4, 1861 McCuskey, the acting Goernor of the new British colony in Lagos wrote:

“The Egba are not at war for the protection of Ijaye as they first alleged but that Ibadan must be driven entirely from the territory they occupy before they will make peace”⁵⁵.

On the November 1, 1861, the Apesi, an Egba chief, speaking on behalf of the Alake, to captain Bedinfield, a British Naval officer, stated an equivocally at Abeokuta that the Egba “were determined never to give up the struggle till the Ibadan had altogether left the Egba lands. If the Ibadans would do it peacefully, there would at once be an end to the war”⁵⁶. It is obvious from the Apesi’s statement that the Egba determination was to reoccupy not only Ijaye but all their erstwhile territories and thus fulfill one of their ulterior motives in allying themselves to the Ijaye. However, when they realized on March 17, 1862 that the

⁵⁴ C4957: Statement of Apenas mission to the king of Ijebu by the Lagos community, Enclosure I in Sir S. Rove to the Rt Hm. The Earl of Derby February, 15, 1883

⁵⁵ C.M.S., CS2/061, Journal of T.king, 6 June, 1860

⁵⁶ Iwelrohin, Nov 22, 1860, August 6, 1861, Oct 25, 1861

Ibadan had gained the upper hand in the war and that their political objective would not be achieved, they abandoned Ijaye on March 17, 1862.⁵⁷

Thirdly the alliance contributed to the distress of the people of Ijaye during the period of the war. Revd. Adolphus Mann complained seriously about the activities of the Egba warriors alleging that they embarked on systematic public robbery. According to him, the Egba warriors swarmed the gate and market places robbing passer-by and wounding people who resisted them. He stated that the children whom the Ijaye pawned to the Egba for food were sold as slaves in the market of Oke Odan. He gave the following eye-witness accounting of Egba atrocities to Major Straith in February 1861:

*Afore my own eye, men and women are stripped of their clothes,
children taken in the streets and carried aaway, my own servants
in the white men's shool were 4 times attaked my boy, robbeed of his
cloth and such as complained to the Egbahiefs go away comfortless.*⁵⁸

In 1862, Governor Freeman disclosed in Lagos that the Egba sold a greater number of Ijaye into slavery more than the Ibadan did on June 4, 1862. He wrote thus:

⁵⁷ F.O 84/1141, McCoskry to Russel, 4 Oct, 1861

⁵⁸ Iwelrohin, Nov 25, 1860

*It is moreover a fact that the Egba kidnapped and sent down to the coast to be sold into slavery a greater number of the people of Ijaye whom they professed to be protecting than did the Ibadan who regarded them as rebels.....*⁵⁹

Some Egba Christians were bought and enslaved Ijaye victims. For instance, among the slaves of Henry Robin, an Egba Christian, were an Ijaye woman and her son called Akintunde.

4.2 Impact of the Alliance on the Egba

For the Egba, the alliance also had its weak and woes. Though they failed to regain their old homesteads, the Egba made brisk business during the period of the war. Egba's trade in foodstuffs and arms and war boosted. The Ijaye were reported streaming to Abeokuta in great caravans numbering from 4,000 to 5,000 people escorted by a large number of armed men to buy grains such as corn, awuje beans and other food items.⁶⁰ As a result of increasing demands by Ijaye people Egba traders travelled to purchase foodstuffs from the Awari in Ota market.

The influx of the Egba traders in the market forced the price of food items to Abeokuta for food stuffs, the price of corn in Ota market was said to have risen

⁵⁹ J.F.A Ajayi And Robert Smith op cit. pp 110

⁶⁰ C.M.S CA2/066, Mann to Major Straith, 7 Feb, 1861

from 15 strings (6d 15k) to 54 strings (1s 9d) approximately 20k for a basket. Corns were bought there at this rate by Egba traders who on getting to Abeokuta sold their purchases at 5 heeds that is 8s 4d (84k) per basket.⁶¹

Like foodstuffs, arms and ammunitions were in great demand. The IweIrohin trade report of December 5, 1860 stated “As article actually in demands, we could only mention powder, shot and run. The importation of guns having a late considerable...”⁶² In September 1861, the Apesi Kemta speaking for the Alake requested for merchant from Lagos to bring good supplies of guns, powder and shots. The cost of gun at that period ranged from a heeds of cowries (16s 1^{1/2}d, approximately, #1.61k) to 11 heeds (19s 8^{1/2}d) while a bag of 211B shot cost from 10 heeds to 11 heeds. The Ijaye purchased arms and ammunitions through Abeokuta. They brought their captives there for sale in exchange for food and arms. The Alake even accused them, in November 1861, of selling their own people to purchase food ammunition⁶³. The Egbas thus derived economic advantage from the Ijaye misfortune. This conclusion is reinforced by Revd Wood’s letter to Henry Venn in June, 1863:

Abeokuta notwithstanding the war has been carrying on trade

to a large extent and so far from decaying as Ibadan is said to be,

⁶¹ F. O. 84/120, Deposition of Awa a slave women of Henry Robin at Abeokuta Dec 12, 1865

⁶²IweIrohin, August 24, 1860

⁶³IweIrohin Dec 22, 1860

*Abeokuta appears only to be getting richer*⁶⁴.

However, despite the above mentioned advantage the Egbas were not totally free from economic problem at this period. As a result of their involvement in the war, they were forced to close the trade route passing through their territory to the coast from the interior in order to prevent Ibadan from getting supplies of arms and ammunition. The closure adversely affected trade in palm oil produced mainly in the interior of Yorubaland. Reports indicated that palm oil was very scarce and costly throughout the period of war. In May 1860, it cost 7^{1/2} heeds per 10 imperial gallons. In November 1861, the heeds price had risen to 12 heeds per 10 imperial gallons. By October 1862, it had reached 15heed per 10 imperial gallons. In September 1861, a commentary in IweIrohin lamented the situation as follows:

*... Now suppose that during the last eighteen month, a quarter or even a tenth part of the young men engaged in war (and consequently eating more than they grow) had been at work here, what a quantity of cotton and palm oil might have been sent out of the country, and of money and goods got back in return*⁶⁵

⁶⁴IweIrohin Dec 5, 1860

⁶⁵IweIrohin, Sept, 25, 1861

Farming was adversely affected as able bodied men who would have engaged in it were drafted to the battlefield. Consequently, the Egba did not totally escape from the scarcity of food (though on a lesser scale than that of Ijaye or Ibadan) that accompanied the war. Available provision could not meet the demands of the Ijaye people and price rose astronomically. For instance, in December 1860, the price of yam was said to have risen to threefold of what it was in November (“about a month ago”) 68 corns was also reported to be exceedingly dear.

In January 1861, the rapid rise in the price of provision in Abeokuta was said to be causing great trouble and anxiety in the town. Two additional causes adduced for the rise in the price or provision were crop failure and “the great grain that Ijaye proves upon the resources of Abeokuta”⁶⁶.

Politically, the alliance had positive and negative effect on the Egba. It ensures closer political relations between them and the people of Ijebu-Ode kingdom than hitherto. Before the mid -19th century, relations between the Egba Ijebu had viewed the settlement of the Egba at Abeokuta with apprehension. They had allied with the Ibadan to destroy the new town in 1832 but their attacks had been repulsed at the battle of owiwi⁶⁷. After this battle hostility between the Egba

⁶⁶ C.M.S., CA2/096, Wood to venn 6 Jun, 1863

⁶⁷ Iwelrohin May 23, 1860

and the Ijebu persisted till 1852 when the Ooni of Ife intervened to reconcile them⁶⁸.

However, in spite of the reconciliation, an atmosphere of mutual suspicion pervaded their relation until the late 1850's when the Ibadan's meteoric rise to power, its imperial ambition and its thrust towards the coast made them realize the need to come together to defend their middle-man's position and their political sovereignty. As a result of these common interests, the Ijebu, except those of Ijebu-Remo area, supported Egba-Ijaye alliance. While the Egba fought on the battle field at Ijaye, the people of Ijebu Ode closed their roads to Ibadan. They raided Ibadan farms and attacked its tributary town in Apomu⁶⁹.

In the spirit of the alliance, the Awujale of Ijebu Ode invited the Egba to help him chastise the Ijebu Remo after the fall of Ijaye. The Ijebu Remo people had supported the Ibadan and opened road to them in defiance to the Awujale's order. The Egba fought the Remo, who were aided by the Ibadan, at Makun, Oru, Ipara and Kutuje between 1862 and 1864. In 1864, they besieged Ikorodu which they accused of aiding the Ibadan and also attacking Egba warrior encamped in Makun⁷⁰.

⁶⁸Iwelrohin, Nov 5, 1861

⁶⁹Iwelrohin, Oct 4, 1861

⁷⁰Iwelrohin, Sept 25, 1861

However, as their continued involvement in these wars in the interior of Yorubaland to the disruption and even closure of trade roads, the Egba offended that British friends who desired to have uninterrupted trade link with the interior Yoruba people. In particular, the British colonial government in Lagos resented the Egba's siege of Ikorodu, an important maritime town and a rendezvous between coasted merchants and traders from the interior.

The Egba defied the British ultimatum to raise their siege of the towns. On March 23, 1865, their warriors were consequently attacked and driven away from the town by a detachment of the West Indian regiment sent from Lagos by Governor Hanley Glover, Anglo-Egba relations remained strained about three years after this episode.⁷¹

⁷¹ Ibid, Dec 22, 1860

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 CONCLUSION

5.1 IMPLICATION FOR INTRA AND INTER-GROUP RELATIONS

The alliance had some implications for intra and inter-group relations among the Yoruba in the second half of the nineteenth century. Firstly, it pushed the hostilities between the Ibadan-Oyo allies and the Ijayero an irreconcilable limit. As earlier indicated, these Oyo-Yoruba people had on the eve of the war shared sentiments of brotherhood. Indeed, there had been attempts in Ibadan Oyo and even in Ijaye to reduce the conflict to personality clash between Kurumi, the Alaafin and the Ibadan chiefs. For instance, Balogun Ibikunle of Ibadan had persuaded Ibadan chiefs against war with Ijaye stressing that Kurumi, the non-conforming Aare-Ona Kakanfo, was old and would soon die, that after his death relations would naturally be established between Ibadan and Ijaye and the Ijaye people would recongnised the Alaafin's authority.

Similar sentiments were apparently expressed in Oyo where the war was initially regarded as against Kurumi and not against the entire people of Ijaye. As shown earlier, the cavalry officers of Ijaye and Ibadan had sworn not to fire shots on the battle fields before Egba entered the war on the Ijaye side.

All these were evidence of caution on either side because of family ties and feelings of brotherhood. When the Egba formally allied with Ijaye, issues such as political and military supremacy in Yorubaland, the control of trade route, and the recovery of homesteads which transcends local disputes among the contending Oyo-Yoruba parties made the Ibadan and the Oyo to determine to fight a total war against the Ijaye brothers and their allies.

Secondly, it engendered internal dissention in Ijebuland, while the Ijebu-Ode people closed road against Ibadan, the people of Ijebu-Remo refused to associate themselves with their counterparts' action. Hoping to derive economic advantage from the closure of Ijebu-Ode routes, they opened routes to the Ibadan through their territory to Ikorodu in defiance of the Awujale's order. The resultant hostility, as we have seen, was the Awujale-sponsored invasion of the Ijebu-Remo territory.

Thirdly, the alliance not only ensures cordial political relations between the Egba of Abeokuta and the Ijebu of Ijebu-Ode, it also foreshadowed the direction of the Grand Alliance against Ibadan between 1877 and 1893. Having realized the need for concerted efforts to defend their economic and political interests against the Oyo-Yoruba people of Ibadan, the Egba and the Ijebu maintained their close political ties after the Ijaye war. Thus when the Ekiti and the Ijesha formed a politico-military alliance against Ibadan, they were supported by the Egba, the

Ijebu of Ijebu-Ode kingdom as well as other groups of the Yoruba who sympathized with the erstwhile Ijaye and Egba allies.

Finally, the alliance failed to retain political equilibrium in Oyo-Yorubaland. Unlike in the Batedo war of 1845, the Egbas military aid to the Ijaye between 1860 and 1862 could not ensure a stalemate that would have maintained the status quo power relations between Ibadan and Ijaye. The destruction of the latter saw the emergence of the former as the supreme military and political power among Oyo-Yoruba towns. Until 1877, Ibadan's military and political supremacy in both the Oyo-Yoruba and the eastern parts of Yorubaland remained virtually unchanged. Only the Egba and the Ijebu had prevented Ibadan from eventually emerging from Ijaye war as a power exercising political and military hegemony over the whole of Yorubaland.

The alliance engendered as sort of permanent animosity between the Ibadan and the Egba. The Ibadan presently ally with other Yoruba while the Egba continue to betray the Yoruba as they considered themselves non-typical Yoruba. That is why in contemporary Nigeria's politics the Egba are unwilling tools in the hand of Northern oligarchy to deny other Yoruba the leadership of the country. The Egba are always seen to be betraying the Yoruba course.

Also few Ibadan people live in Abeokuta while very few Egba live in Ibadan as well. The Egba population is very small when compared with Ijebu and other Yoruba people.

The destruction of Ijaye by Ijaye and the failure of other Yoruba people to reactivate it and resettle in Ijaye, to bring it back to its former glory shows that Yoruba people had no sympathy to the Ijaye course even after the 1862/68 war against Ijaye. Ijaye has been completely destroyed in the map of Nigeria as a result of the 1862/68 war against Ibadan.

The military superiority of Ibadan over Ijaye and over combined forces of Ijaye and Egba served as an indication to the colonial masters that Ibadan had to be weakened and captured militarily and diplomatically to renounce its political leadership over the towns so that it could be easily brought under colonial rule and also wakes the process of colonialisation faster.

The military prowess of Ibadan had waned considerably in modern times as emphasis has changed from military power to civil king in becoming highest rank of political leadership. However, the hierarchical structure makes succession a very smooth one but inhibit the installation of an agile, young, dynamic and educated person as king.

The hierarchy still remains intact but it is characterized with lack of innovativeness and dynamism

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